

urban
PERISCOPE
IFC Manual

The Project **Urban PERISCOPE** INTEGRATED/0918/0034 is co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund and the Republic of Cyprus through the Research Innovation Foundation.

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Abstract

This document is intended to serve as a guide for the UP BIM team, handling IFC data and providing a better understanding of the settings available within BIM software, such as Autodesk Revit, discussing how they can influence the quality and content of IFC files. Since the UP BIM team will use Autodesk Revit as the main BIM modelling software, the present session serves as an IFC Revit manual and sets out the basics of IFC by explaining in detail how to export, link and open IFC files.

This guideline document integrates state-of-the-art documentation and instructions published in the literature:

- CADconsulting, REVIT IFC Manual, online,
https://issuu.com/cadconsulting/docs/revit_ifc_manual
- Autodesk Revit IFC manual INSTRUCTIONS FOR REVIT USERS

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IFC FILES

The Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) are an open standard for the exchange of information within a project in different faces as design, construction, procurement, maintenance, etc. and across different software. These files have different data associated with different elements, procedures, working groups, or concepts, which should be organized in a certain way to be easily analyzed and discovered. For example, if an element is a physical object, like walls and floors, it can have a geometric representation association with them, and allow the BIM users to have them digitally in 2D or 3D representations. IFC is an attempt to improve the interoperability of BIM data in the UP project by creating a technical specification that the UP BIM authors should follow. Moreover, IFC is an Official International Standard (ISO 16739-1:2018 standard) of how BIM data should be stored. In the following link, the UP BIM working team can find a detailed list of all the applications with certified IFC support buildingSMART:

<https://www.buildingsmart.org/compliance/software-certification/certified-software/>.

Figure 1 – IFC Standard Workflow

1.1 IFC project declaration in Revit

The most fundamental concept related to the IFC files is the ability to declare *the Project*. The project is not a visible element in Revit, but it does have attributes associated with it. The most necessary values for these attributes are derived from the tab *Project Information* settings. The following list explains in detail what these attributes are, and which tabs the UP BIM team should edit to set them correctly:

- GlobalId – (IFC Global Unique Identifier Attribute) is set automatically and cannot be modified via the UI (User Interface). It can, however, be modified via the Revit API (Application Program Interface).
- OwnerHistory - set automatically.
- Name - this is the *Short Name* or code of the project, it can be set by changing the *Project Number* attribute.
- Description - this field can be set by creating a new project parameter called *IfcDescription*, and making it available to the *Project Information* category. The UP BIM team must ensure that this parameter is grouped under the named *IFC Parameters*. More details about the creation of a new project parameter can be found at:

<https://knowledge.autodesk.com/support/revit-products/learn-explore/caas/CloudHelp/cloudhelp/2019/ENU/Revit-Model/files/GUID-28CBBEC2-6262-42D3-AE41-B36166E8318F-htm.html>

Figure 2 – IFC project declaration in Revit – Name attribute

- ObjectType - this field can be set by creating a new project parameter under the name *IfcObjectType* and making it available to the *Project Information* category. The UP BIM working group must ensure that groups this parameter is under a group named *IFC Parameters*.
- LongName – the present field consists of the full project name, and can be set by changing the *Project Name* attribute.
- Phase - the project phase is set by the *Project Status* attribute.
- RepresentationContexts - Revit will automatically define only one representation context, which will be a 3-dimensional model, with a coordinate system and true north.
- UnitsInContext - the units are taken from the *Project Units* settings.
- ExportAs – overwrites the default IFC class of a Revit component for the IFC export. The parameter value *dontexport* on the other hand prevents the creation of a component type when exporting the data model.
- Ifcexport type parameter overwrites the default type for the IFC export. This parameter is not used often since the type can also be defined by the *ifcExportAs* parameter, where the type is separated after the class with a colon.
- The coordinate system of the *IfcGeometricRepresentationContext* is used to define the offset of the project coordinates from the global point of origin. This seems to always be set to (0, 0, 0). By default, true north is Y, east is X, and up / elevation is Z. Please note that the *IfcProject* does not define the site location.

It is worth to be noted that the UP-BIM working group can propagate shared parameters, and IFC allows the working group to create project libraries that define either type of objects or groups of properties (known as property sets in IFC lingo). Technically, the UP-BIM team could create their own families in IFC format, and it can have parametric data stored within it. Furthermore, according to the hierarchy, export parameters are above the default settings of the mapping table in the IFC export settings and thus overwrite the default settings. The parameter names are defined in the IFC format and are only used/accepted if the spelling is correct. IFC export parameters should be assigned when they are integrated into the group *IFC parameters*.

1.1.2 Project and Loadable families

A family created within the UP projects can be assigned to any class officially supported by Autodesk using the *IfcExportAs* parameter. Loadable families usually behave like project families and can be assigned to any supported class. It is also possible to assign nested families to different classes and types of IFC export. It is important to ensure that the *shared* option is activated in the properties of the individual families.

1.2 IFC file formats

.ifc : Standard format, based on STEP- Standard for the Exchange of Product Model Data

.ifcZIP Compressed IFC files with much smaller file size; can be read by most software application that supports IFC. It can be unpacked to make the uncompressed IFC file visible.

.ifcXML XML-based representation of IFC data, required by certain calculation software.

1.3 IFC Versions

The IFC versions are updated and developed by buildingSMART. It is recommended that the UP-BIM working group use the latest versions. Also, it should be taken under consideration that the IFC4 format allows a better representation of complex geometries.

Current versions:

- IFC4 (still in beta, certification process in progress, offers certain advanced possibilities but is not widely supported yet);
- IFC2x3 (currently the most supported and stable format, certified in Revit and recommended for production);
- IFC2x2 (recommended if the recipient of the file does not have software with IFC2x3 or IFC4 support).

1.4 Model view definition (MVD)

The term Model View Definition (MVD) determines how the UP BIM authors use an IFC file through the activation of specific data exchange scenarios. MVDs are used for the targeted exchange of specialized models, taking account of the graphic and content related information that the planner needs. For this reason, the UP-BIM team should create a specialized model according to the requirements of a cultural heritage model. The official buildingSMART- defined MVDs available in Revit are listed below:

- IFC4: The MRV (Model Reference View) was designed for the standard delivery of a reference model for specialist planners in IFC4. It provides an IFC model for coordination and model-based quantity determination, as referred to in the modelling software. The model is not necessarily heavily simplified in graphic terms; it serves merely as a reference that may be quite detailed but it not editable, so further work on the geometry cannot be conducted. IFC4 usually contains only the most essential geometric definitions.
- IFC2x3 Coordination View Version 2.0: This MVD is primarily used for exchanging architectural, building technology, and construction engineering models. It is optimized for the coordinated exchange of BIM models between the main disciplines in the building industry. Coordination View 2.0—also known as CV 2.0—is currently the most widely used and supported Model View Definition.
- IFC2x3 COBie 2.4 Design Deliverable: IFC format equivalent to the COBie (Construction Operations Building Information Exchange) output required by the UK government for their 2016 Level 2 BIM mandate for collaboration on public-sector work. For exporting in COBie format, the relevant addon from <https://www.biminteroperabilitytools.com> can also be installed.
- IFC2x2 Coordination View: This MRV is used only in isolated cases, such as when exporting MVDs for software that does not support IFC2x3. Each of these MVDs can naturally be adapted to the needs of the workflow.

To identify which MVD is used by an existing IFC file, it is suggested to open the file in a text editor. The header contains all the information about the MVD, the exact IFC exporter version and the software that it has been exported from:

- * Date: Wed Jul 08 14:56:20 2020
- * Produced by: The EXPRESS Data Manager Version 5.02.0100.07: 28 Aug 2013
- * Module: EDMstepFileFactory/EDMstandAlone
- * Host: HPCF/UP Platform
- * Database: <https://drive.hpcf.cyi.ac.cy/index.php/s/xBfENn5xdNDWQFH> * Database version: 5507
- * Database creation date: Wed Jul 08 14:56:20 2020

- * Model to populate: DataRepository.ifcimport
- * Header model to populate:
- * Step file name: UPCYI_ARC_STR578_001_WIP.ifc
- * EDMuser: sdai-user
- * EDMgroup: sdai-group
- * License ID and type: 5605: Permanent license. Expiry date:
- * EDMstepFileFactory options: 010201000002

 Operation terminated successfully.

1.5 IFC Structure

An IFC file describes a building model based on a pre-defined information structure that represents the building model. When it is saved, the IFC file standard orders the IFC units hierarchically according to their type, as in the following link. For a list of all buildingSMART-defined classes, see <https://autode.sk/IFClinks>.

Figure 3 –The IFC Tree Structure

1.5.1 IFC Classes and Types

Based on the *Autodesk Revit IFC Manual*, IFC files are defined objects within the IFC data models. Depending on the assignment of a building entity and type definition, these objects are allocated specific default attributes and dependencies according to the IFC schema. That's why the selection of the right entity is crucial when exporting a model as IFC. For instance, if a wall is not assigned to the entity *IfcWall*, it is not allocated all the attributes that are required for it to be described clearly. This means that it will not be interpreted correctly as a wall by other software. Distinctions are made not

only between major categories, so that components can also be assigned as entities, in order for them to be reproduced more accurately in the IFC data model. This classification of entities can roughly be compared to the sub-categories in Revit. A foundation of the *IfcFooting* entity can also be shown, depending on the type of component and its intended use. Using this logic results in complex structures that enable the generation of a data model in which every element can be geometrically and alphanumerically represented and identified. For more details the UP- BIM working group can find in the following link: https://damassets.autodesk.net/content/dam/autodesk/drafter/2528/180213_IFC_Handbuch.pdf

Class Allocation

What am I?

Type Definition

More accurate allocation

Interaction

Which objects can I affect?

Geometry

What are my measures?

Relationships

What objects are superior or interior to me?

Standard Attributes

What information do I generally provide?

Figure 4 – IFC classes and types diagram

1.5.2 Geometric representation of IFC objects

There are 4 basic methods of producing geometrical representations of a three-dimensional IFC object, by:

- Extrusion;
- Solid-body representation using a sweep;
- Representation using B-reps; and,
- NURBS and other smooth surfaces.

1.5.3. IFC object definitions and object type definitions in Revit

Revit categories like walls, floors, ceilings, and columns can be defined as such in IFC: *IfcWall*, *IfcSlab*, *IfcCovering*, and *IfcColumn*, respectively. Actually, the IFC standard has more object *classes* than what is defined in Revit and offers higher granularity, responding to the needs of more disciplines than architectural engineering. Therefore, when the UP-team exports to an IFC, all the Revit categories should be *mapped* to IFC object *classes*. All object occurrences are defined by a mapping table supplied by Autodesk that maps Revit family categories to IFC objects. The UP authors can find this in the following tab by going to *File> Export> Options> IFC Options*. IFC objects are defined as subclasses of *IfcObject*, whereby the UP team will most commonly be dealing with subclasses of *IfcProduct*, such as walls, beams, etc.

In detail, the mapping table has two columns- figure 5:

- *IFC Class Name*; and,
- *IFC Type*.

Figure 5 – Autodesk Revit IFC Object mapping configuration dialog

Attention must be paid to the fact that the *IFC Type* field does *not* refer to the IFC object type. For example, an *IfcBeam* has an associated *IfcBeamType*, which serves a purpose similar to a parent class to which attributes/property sets / geometric representations can be inherited from (and override in the child). The IFC Type field refers to *PredefinedType* attribute that exists for both IFC objects and IFC object types. These are more detailed subcategories of the semantic IFC class name. For example, an *IfcBeam* has a *PredefinedType* attribute which may contain an enum of *IfcBeamTypeEnum*, where the UP BIM working group can specify their beam to be a *beam*, *joist*, *hollowcore*, *lintel* etc.

There is a fundamental problem in Revit whereby the semantic object BIM users are modelling determines what modelling capabilities they have. If a BIM author wants to model a roof, he might use some tools as floors, because geometrically these tools can be very similar. This leads to users misusing objects for inappropriate IFC types. However, the following example explains in detail the proper way to mitigate this by ensuring that it is exported correctly into IFC, regardless of the Revit category being used.

If the UP BIM modeller adds a project parameter called *IfcExportAs*, as a text parameter and place it in the *IFC Parameters* group, then the BIM user can override the IFC class and predefined type on an instance-by-instance or type-by-type basis. For instance, if the BIM modeller creates a new generic in-place model, and type in *IfcCovering*, and export it into an IFC, it will turn into an *IfcCovering* object. If the BIM user alternatively types *IfcCovering.SKIRTINGBOARD*, he will export it as an *IfcCovering* object, and its *PredefinedType* attribute will be set to *SKIRTINGBOARD*. This pattern of *IfcClass.ENUMVALUEINUPPERCASE* generally works for all classes and types and this is a way of adding

semantics to generic models. However, the BIM modellers should keep in their mind that this trick only works with user-created families and in-place models. It does *not* work on system families.

1.5.4 Default Attributes and Parameters

One of the key considerations when transferring IFC data models is the provision of information that can be correctly converted, analysed, integrated, interpreted and evaluated by UP users and their planning and calculation tools, regardless of the internal file attribute structure and descriptions in the respective applications the users operate with. Each IFC object subclass has a series of attributes that are composed of the attributes of that particular class, as well as the attributes inherited by any parent classes. In the latest IFC4Add2 specification, it is now very easy to see this data tree, as each IFC object page has a section called *Attribute Inheritance*, which lists the history of attributes inherited. In addition, new IFC properties can be formulated across the board using default attributes. These attributes are stored in the IFC definition and are named in English language. Some BIM software suites can automatically assign internal attributes to IFC-compliant default attributes. This ensures that the necessary information is provided to represent an object and that these attributes are related to the IFC object definitions and object type definitions (chapter 1.5.3. *IFC object definitions and object type definitions in Revit*).

For instance, an *IfcWall* inherits *GlobalId*, *OwnerHistory*, *Name*, and *Description* from its parent *IfcRoot*. The UP BIM modeller will notice that this is the same as *IfcProject*. However, in the same way as in *IfcProject* the *Name* field is special, the *Name* field of an *IfcWall* is also special (this applies to most *IfcObject* children). By default, this field will be named after the family name, followed by the family type name, followed by the family type *tag*, which is an autogenerated numerical ID. These three values are concatenated together with the “.” symbol as a separator. If it is an in-place family, it will use the in-place model name twice as the first two fields.

If the UP BIM team wants a meaningful name, it can set its *Name* value manually. The user should create a parameter called *IfcName* and add it to the *IFCParameters* group. This is the same technique used to set the *Description* attribute. Please note that the IFC exporter only transmits valid property values, i.e. those that are not empty. If the parameter is missing from the IFC file, this is likely because the Revit parameter does not have a value. This operation optimizes the file size, as empty data fields are not exported. This pattern of adding a parameter named after the attribute and prefixed with *Ifc* is common to all attributes. For instance, an *IfcWall* also has an attribute called *Tag*. The UP-working group can set the value of *Tag* by creating a parameter called *IfcTag*. An overview of all default parameters defined in IFC format is provided by buildingSMART in the form of parameter sets (P-sets). As an example, below the default parameters of a wall:

Pset_Wall Common

Default parameters in Revit:

- Reference** Component type (type name)
- Fire Rating** Fire-resistance class (type parameter)
- Thermal Transmittance** U-value (type parameter)
- Is External** Exterior component (type parameter, given as yes/no)
- Load Bearing** Load-bearing (instance parameter)
- Extend To Structure** Fixed on top (behaviour)

The following parameters are also part of the Pse Wall Common, but are either unavailable or not assigned by default in Revit:

- Acoustic Rating** Sound insulation class

Combustible Combustible material

Surface Spread of Flame Fire behaviour

Compartmentation Fire compartment-defining component

For these parameters to appear in Revit, they have to be created using the exact name, the correct type (text/number/yes/no, visible in the buildingSMART documentation).

As soon as these parameters become available and acquire a value, they can be taken into account in the export into IFC. The advantage of this standardization is that the respective parameters of other software are automatically recognized and assigned correctly.¹

1.6. Exporting IFC files

In the IFC file, each object or type has a list of related sets of fields which apply to it. Some of these are specific to the respective class of IFC object, and some apply to many objects. Before exporting IFC files it is important to check the settings. Revit> Export> Options> IFC options.

Revit categories are assigned to IFC classes using a mapping table – figure 5. This table is stored as a text file (*.txt) and can be customized directly in Revit or by using a text editor.

As the authors have already mentioned, the first column, the Revit category, is unchangeable and automatically lists all the categories and sub-categories available in the Revit project. The IFC class name column contains the IFC class to which the sub-category or category should be assigned. If the category is not to be exported, the UP BIM modeller can enter *Not Exported*. However, Revit is delivered with basic settings that meet a certain basic standard.

The second column is related to the IFC classes and type. This field must be entered manually, with the correct spelling. In this way, the footings from the IFC class become assigned to the *IfcFooting*. The list of classes supported in Revit is regularly updated and can be called up here: <https://autode.sk/IFClinks>.

An IFC type can also be assigned which, like the sub-categories in Revit, allows more accurate differentiation within a category. The types available in IFC format can be checked for their respective IFC release on the buildingSMART page. The pre-configured mapping table is stored by default via the system path “C:\ProgramData\Autodesk\RVT(Version)\exportlayers-ifc-IAI.txt”. A standardized export can be performed across different UP stakeholders using a centrally stored mapping table. It is worth noting that, unlike Revit, certain BIM software suites do not only work with categories but also with the layers used in CAD operations. For more details, the UP team can find the following link: https://damassets.autodesk.net/content/dam/autodesk/drafter/2528/180213_IFC_Handbuch.pdf.

¹ Remove incorrect mapping like:

Curtain Wall Panels by default export to *IfcCurtainWall* this should be **IfcPlateType**

Curtain Wall Mullions by default export to *IfcCurtainWall* this should be **IfcMemberType**

Plumbing Fixtures by default are mapped to *IfcFlowTerminal* which is a high-level entity. This has been used because plumbing fixtures can be exported to *IfcSanitaryTerminalType* or *IfcWasteTerminalType* but this creates an incorrect export. **IfcBuildingElementProxyType** should be used for any situations like this (there are many) just to follow one consistent rule. These have to be overridden at element level.

For a boiler family *IfcExportAs* is **IfcBoilerType**.

For a floor finish modelled using the floor category **IfcCoveringType** should be used.

For a pile (because there is no type in IFC) **IfcPile** should be used - note that even though *IfcExportAs* is a Revit type parameter it can still be used.

1.6.1. Setting Export Settings.

The UP- BIM team can export IFC properly set data by checking these two boxes in the IFC setup settings.

Figure 6 – Export IFC – Main dialog

- Main dialogue: The desired name and file location of the IFC file to be exported are specified under the *Name Convention Document*. Currently selected setup: allows export according to preset configurations. The selection of the schema and MVD to be used is crucial in defining the content and structure of the IFC file and should, therefore, be coordinated and chosen according to their intended use.
- Modify setup: these settings can be adapted if required and custom definitions can be created, which are stored with the Revit project. When exporting several heritage buildings within the UP project, the same settings must be used for all files and saved to an IFC file.

1.6.2 General Settings

The following general settings can be found in the general tab in Advanced IFC export settings – Figure 7. The IFC version allows the UP BIM working group to select the IFC schema and the MVD, as explained in detail earlier in this manual. The most commonly used schema is IFC 2x3 Coordination View 2.0, as it is supported by most programs. The file type determines the file format in which the exported file will be saved. For big projects, the compressed *.ifczip format can be used, which is also supported by most IFC viewers. If required, the *.ifczip file can be unzipped to get the uncompressed *.ifc file.

Figure 7 – Revit IFC property set export settings

Regarding the Property set, the UP team doesn't need to fill in any data. In contrast, Revit has properties which always show even if it is not necessary to fill them in, and the absence of information may sometimes be misinterpreted as intentional data (such as the default value of a boolean checkbox). This is known as the NULL vs empty problem in Revit and can mislead UP BIM users. For instance, an *IfcWall* can have the *Pset_WallCommon* property set applied to it. This property set has attributes such as *AcousticRating*, *FireRating*, *ThermalTransmittance*, *LoadBearing* and so on. Although there is room for improvement, there is generally a sensible set of attributes defined in IFC.

Also, if the *IfcWall* is concrete, the UP BIM modeller can use the *Pset_ConcreteElementGeneral* and describe attributes such as *ConstructionMethod* (In-Situ/Precast), *StrengthClass*, and *ReinforcementVolumeRatio*, among others. If the wall isn't concrete, the UP BIM modellers should simply exclude this property set. If the UP BIM modellers have additional details specific to a heritage building project, then they can create new property sets and save it on the UP BIM Library and create the missing attributes. Ideally, the UP BIM modellers should create an *IfcProjectLibrary* so that UP platform users know what information to expect that exists in the platform about the heritage building, but as mentioned above, it is not possible to create project libraries in Revit. However, the UP team have created an online BIM library where the users are able to download or store ifcfamilies on the following link: <https://drive.hpcf.cyi.ac.cy/index.php/s/Qq99EJ3Jci8RZqM>

The table below presents the most common correspondence between elements categories and IFC classes. The UP BIM working group should adapt to the case heritage buildings and their elements and implement further this part of the document.

ELEMENT CATEGORY	CLASSI IFC
Furniture	IfcFurniture
Caseworks (fixed furniture)	IfcFurniture

Shaft	IfcOpeningElement
Ceilings	IfcCovering
Windows	IfcWindow
Foundation	IfcSlab, IfcFooting, IfcPile
Spaces/Rooms	IfcSpace
Curtain walls structure	IfcMember, IfcPlate
Walls	IfcWall, IfcCurtainWall
Curtain walls panels	IfcPlate, IfcDoor, IfcMember
Flooring	IfcSlab
Columns	IfcColumn
Structural Columns	IfcColumn
Doors	IfcDoor
Ramps	IfcRamp, IfcRampFlight, IfcSlab
Railings	IfcRailing, IfcMember
Stairs	IfcStair
Stairs - landing	IfcStair, IfcSlab
Stairs - flight	IfcStairFlight
Stairs - structure	IfcMember
Curtain wall systems	IfcCurtainWall
Structural beam system	IfcElementAssembly
Structural grid	IfcBeam, IfcMember
Roofing	IfcRoof
Roofing – drain pipe	IfcPipeSegment
Slabs	IfcSlab
Trusses	IfcElementAssembly

1.6.2.1 Project Origin

The UP BIM modellers should define the origin of the exported file. There are 4 options:

- Current shared coordinates origin;
- Internal Revit coordinates;
- Project Basepoint;
- Site Survey point;

All the UP-built heritage models must be exported with the current shared coordinates origin.

1.6.2.2 Split walls, Supports and Air ducts by level

Split walls, supports, and air ducts by level and divide these elements if they have been modelled over several floors. They are divided according to the floors of the building. This setting can be determined for each floor in the Revit properties. The definition of the right level as floors is considered very important otherwise the IFC structure will become confusing and the elements will not separate optimally. Ideally, a project will have one level for each floor.

1.6.2.3 File Header Information / Project Address

File Header information/project address allows general project information delivered with the IFC file to be customized. File information can be viewed with a text editor and, in addition to the optional information, automatically provides information about the software used to generate the file, the IFC exporter, and the IFC schema. This information is mainly relevant to IFC exports for a CAFM platform in COBie format. It is recommended to the UP-BIM team to use the COBie Extension for Revit for this purpose, available at <http://www.biminteroperabilitytools.com/>. Moreover, the project information is partially based on the location of the building (via address details). The information on the IFC export dialogue can be used to supplement or overwrite these data.

1.6.2.4 Additional Content

Additional content can be found in the Advanced IFC export settings.

- Export plan view elements enable the export of some 2D elements such as grids, text, and lines. It is vital to ensure that the correct classes are used, such as `IfcAnnotation` or `IfcGrid` for grids. However, not all IFC viewers support the display of these classes. 2D support is restricted because the IFC format was designed to export BIM data, i.e. the 3D geometry, including the associated information. As such, it is not possible to export plan views.
 - Export linked files as separate IFCs exports the Revit files that are currently linked within the project as separate IFC files. If this function remains deactivated, the Revit links are not exported.
 - Export-only elements visible in view include only elements that are visible in the current view due to visibility settings, filters, and phases.
 - Export spaces in 3D views generate IFC spaces and 3D volumes that can then be selected in an IFC viewer.

1.6.2.5 Property settings

The property sets can be used to access various other key settings such as:

- Export Revit property sets allow the UP BIM users to export all the properties of a component. Although it might seem desirable at first glance, this function is not recommended for exchanging specialist IFC models.
- Export IFC common property sets include the default properties defined in the IFC schema. This an option should always be activated.

Figure 9 – Revit Property sets tab.

- Export base quantities provide base quantities as a basis for determining quantities and creating simulations. During export, all elements are assigned as *base quantities* (i.e., fixed property sets defined by buildingSMART).

- Export schedules as property sets enable the targeted export of properties that are defined in the schedules. As a Revit project usually contains lots of schedules, this option may be restricted to certain component lists by using only schedules with “IFC”, “Pset” or “default” in their name- Figure 10.

- Exporting user-defined property sets is another way of exporting specific selected properties. The parameters to be exported can also be specified in a text file. The default file is stored at:

C:\ProgramData\Autodesk\ApplicationPlugins\IFC2018.bundle\Contents\2018\DefaultUserDefinedParameterSets.txt

- Classification settings allow the BIM users to specify the uniformity classification used in the project according to a country-specific system. In the UK, for instance, the Uniclass system is established as the means of classification and is delivered with Revit. In this case, the building information modelling comes with unique key numbers for component properties, allowing machine processability and data linking (interoperability). Revit allows using the standardized uniformity classification of components or a custom classification file. This is usually done by assigning the type property *assembly identifier*. This field allows the user to select a pre-defined value from the classification file, which can be found in text format here: C:\ProgramData\Autodesk\Libraries\UnifomatClassifications.txt

<My IFC Wall Parameters>				
A	B	C	D	E
Top Constraint	Bottom Constraint	Length	Unconnected Height	Phase created
Manual	Level 1	14,000 m	4,000 m	Phase 1
Manual	Level 1	13,000 m	4,000 m	Phase 1
Manual	Level 1	14,000 m	4,000 m	Phase 1
Manual	Level 1	13,000 m	4,000 m	Phase 1

Element ID	Element	My IFC Wall Parameters	Pset_WallCom...
Property			Value
	Unconnected Height		4,000 m
	Bottom Constraint		Level 1
	Phase created		Phase 1
	Length		14,000 m

Figure 10 – Revit schedule and the resulting properties in the IFC file.

This file can be adapted in line with the aforementioned local classification system. Information about Autodesk's current modifications to these files can be found on the BIM blog: <https://autode.sk/IFClinks>.

The specification in the IFC export dialogue is merely information about which classification system is being used, and it does not affect the actual content of the model as the following figure (11).

Figure 11 – IFC Classification settings.

1.6.2.6 Level of Detail

The level of detail of certain geometric elements enables the user to set the level of detail. This has a significant impact on the file size and correct interpretation. Components should be exported with a high level of geometric detail only if needed, as it can cause data bloat. The Detail level *low* is usually sufficient.

1.6.2.7 Advanced Settings

The last tab, *Advanced*, allows the BIM modeller to select the following additional options:

- Export parts as building elements are relevant to IFC data exchange when working with partial elements in the construction of walls or floor slabs. Partial elements are exported as *IfcBuildingElementPart* by default. This allows individual parts to be assigned to a higher-level element within the IFC data model.
- Allow use of mixed solid model representation enables the export of combined swept solid and B-rep models. A geometric object in an IFC data model is normally generated from either one or several swept solid objects, or B-rep objects alone. The combination of these two types of representation is not enabled by default in the IFC schema. For more complex components, in particular, this leads either to larger file size or incorrect presentation, as elements are wholly represented B-rep objects. Solid model representation combines the two types of representation within a single class, which can mean better geometric results at a smaller file size for complex models. It should be noted, however, that the IFC file exported using this setting no longer complies with the default IFC schema and must, therefore, be accepted as such by all users accessing the project. For certain areas of application, it may be necessary to have an unaltered default schema for export.

Figure 12 – IFC Advanced settings.

- The use of the active view when creating geometry incorporates the display settings for the current view into the IFC export and was specially developed for building equipment elements, such as cable routes and built-in parts whose model geometry differs from the geometry represented.
 - Using family and type names for reference enables referencing based on Revit family and type. The default setting is for referencing a component based on the types used.
 - Using 2D room boundaries for room volume simplifies the calculation of the room volume based on two-dimensional spatial boundaries. The space geometry from Revit is used to determine the volume in the IFC scheme by default.
 - Include IFCSITE elevation in the site-local placement origin when exporting information about the site, the area (IFC site) has a height value for the project. In IFC2x3 CV2.0, this value is set to “0” by default, which may not be interpreted correctly by older applications. The corresponding value is also provided with the help of this export setting.
 - Store the IFC-GUID in an element parameter after export stores the generated IFC-GUIDs in the *IfcGUID* parameter after they have been successfully exported. This simplifies subsequent specialist model coordination, as the components are identifiable.
 - Export bounding box. Every geometrical element can also be represented in a simplified manner using a bounding box. If an object cannot be exported due to its complex geometry or needs to be simplified to better determine clearances, the bounding box can serve as an alternative to the representation itself or allow the object to be represented altogether.

1.6.2.8 Other Settings

The class assignments made in the IFC export settings are formulated as defaults and form the basis for IFC export, with one IFC class assigned to each Revit category. In some cases, however, a finer division may be necessary, so that components are assigned to different IFC classes within a Revit category, often using the *Generic model* category. By using export parameters, these components can be assigned to specific IFC classes and types regardless of the default settings in the mapping table.

1.7. Use cases

1.7.1 Floor Slab Construction

Floor slabs are often modelled using two separate elements: the supporting floor slab is modelled before the floor structure is added as a multi-layer floor for each room. For IFC export, all floor slabs are assigned to the *IfcSlab* class. This may prove a hindrance to further planning or assignment. Instead, it makes sense to export the floor not as *IfcSlab*, but as *IfcCovering*, which also assigns it the appropriate attributes, such as combustibility or surface finish. As such, for both floor constructions, the *IfcExportAs* parameter is specified as *IfcCovering*. Also to be used *FLOORING*, which assigns the elements to the *IfcCovering* class and the *FLOORING* type on export. This assignment gives the floor construction the right class/type and the properties defined in the *Pset_CoveringCommon*, which facilitates further evaluations.

Figure 13 – Floor slab construction

1.7.2 Assign Default Attributes

BuildingSMART provides appropriate information about default attributes as part of its online documentation. Under the term *Pset_CoveringCommon*, for instance, the user can find all the default attributes of the entity class *IfcCovering*. For a list of the property data sheets for architectural components of the IFC4 schema with multilingual explanations, see the following link: <http://www.buildingsmart-tech.org/ifc/IFC2x4/rc3/html/schema/ifcsharedbldgelements/pset/>

The attributes made available are determined by the choice of class or type. As an example, *Pset_CoveringCommon* has been specified here, so that all elements of the *IfcCovering* class are automatically assigned. For more details:

https://damassets.autodesk.net/content/dam/autodesk/drafter/2528/180213_IFC_Handbuch.pdf

1.7.3 Creating Selected Attributes in Revit Projects

Due to a large amount of data, it does not make sense to provide all the available attributes in a single template. Adding the necessary attributes as required is more practical. Autodesk provides its own IFC shared parameters file, which already contains all the available parameters: <https://autode.sk/IFClinks>

The correct units for the parameters are predefined in this file. The parameters can be defined either as type or as instance parameters. The newly created attributes are assigned to the corresponding *Pset* during export.]

1.7.4 Usage groups in the IFC data model

Usage groups can also be stored within the IFC data model. Based on an export schema generated in Autodesk Revit, these groupings can be shared with all users collaborating on the project for further use. The export of user groups and zones is based on the parameter *ZoneName*. This is assigned as a shared parameter (type: text) of the Revit category *Rooms*. Only one instance parameter can be used for this category. Using this parameter, the user can then generate a colour scheme for rooms/zones and create the necessary categories.

For more details see:

https://damassets.autodesk.net/content/dam/autodesk/drafter/2528/180213_IFC_Handbuch.pdf

1.7.5 Quantity Surveying and Quantity Take-off in Revit

IFC has the concept of a special set of properties which can be set for each object to define quantities. These can be quantities such as counts, lengths, areas, and volumes, and are designed to be useful for quantity surveyors to easily quantify different elements from the BIM model. They are similar to property sets but are treated a little especially under the hood.

Further information related to Quantity Surveying in the context of Urban Periscope can be found at:

<https://thinkmoult.com/how-to-create-better-ifc-files-with-revit.html>